

MDMC

Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

**AMORE: a GUI to promote
migration from paper to eLN**

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Author's Declaration

I, Emanuele D'Amico, declare that this thesis entitled, "*AMORE: a GUI to promote migration from paper to eLN*" and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in CNR-SPIN Naples' MODA Laboratory.
- If any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where the thesis is based on work I have done in collaboration with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I contributed.
- With respect to AI technologies, I acknowledge the use of open source LLM **DeepSeek-R1**:
 - As a source of information to kick-start certain features present within the software described in this document (AMORE);
 - To generate static elements for said software (CSS and JavaScript);
 - To improve my writing style (grammar/spell checking, not content).
- I also acknowledge the use of Reverso Context to provide quick translations for terms and phrases used.
- Last but not least I acknowledge the use of the Merriam-Webster and the Cambridge Dictionary for looking up definitions of (respectively) US and UK English terms and phrases.
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- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

Date:
April 30, 2025

Signed:

*“Why isn’t this working? Is there something missing?
Must more blood be shed?”*

Vergil, *Devil May Cry 3*,
on the wonders of programming Python

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Goodbye Trieste.
May we meet again later.
May I dine many more times in your inns.

Abstract

This thesis presents the development of AMORE (Autonomous Management of Outputs for Research Efficiency), a lightweight web-based software designed to facilitate the transition from traditional and unreliable paper notebooks to a more sophisticated eLN (electronic laboratory notebook) - specifically eLabFTW.

The core objective is the alignment of the data collected by researchers with the FAIR principles. While eLabFTW itself already provides the tools to pursue this objective an additional step was needed to enforce a certain standard while simplifying the entry of new data and the update of old assets on the eLN: AMORE enforces our own standard in terms of sample nomenclature, provides an elementary sample tracking feature and presents to the user a simple interface to interact with.

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Chapter 1

State of the art and eLabFTW

Modern scientific research relies more and more on digital supports, making it easier to ensure that results harvested from experiments and analysis are managed and curated in compliance with the **FAIR principles**: the collected data must be **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable** and **Reusable**. These principles enhance transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration by structuring data and metadata in a standardized way. FAIR compliance helps researchers and institutions maximize the impact of their work while also meeting funding and publishing requirements - especially important in today's research since funds are always lacking and publishers are always hard to deal with, problems all children of the same common parent, money, but crucial to deal with nonetheless.

Without FAIR practices valuable data risks being lost, misinterpreted or underutilized. This is especially evident in those faculties still using paper laboratory notebooks: while familiar and easy to use these supports lack searchability, backup security, and efficient (or generally any kind of) sharing capabilities. **Electronic Lab Notebooks (eLN's)** address these limitations by enabling structured, version-controlled and easily shareable record-keeping. FAIR-aligned eLN's ensure that experimental data is systematically organized, properly annotated, and stored in sustainable formats.

Adopting an eLN helps researchers transition smoothly from paper while adhering to FAIR principles; in this context the rise of **FOSS (Free, Open-Source Software)** in Data Science has played an extremely important role, with the emergence of many data management tools and eLN's. The subject of this thesis is the process we've followed to incentive the migration from the old-school physical notebook to an eLN of choice - eLabFTW

- through the development of a user-friendly, elementary, open-source graphical user interface (GUI) made to enforce and work with a specific pre-defined internal standard.

1.1 CNR-SPIN laboratories in Naples

CNR-SPIN Naples is currently hosted by the **University of Naples Federico II** and has its laboratories in its Physics Department in Monte Sant'Angelo, Fuorigrotta, Naples (NA). Currently the most important operational laboratory is **MODA** - *Modular Facility for Oxide Deposition and Analysis* - placed in Building 6 (Physics Department) and host of one of the PLD machines related to the NFFA-DI project; later this year a new NFFA-DI laboratory will be opened in Building 8 instead. These laboratories also feature many spectroscopy or fine analysis machines such as an XPS, an SPM, LEED, RHEED and more. Other informations are available on the NFFA-DI website's catalogue.

1.1.1 Issues

As stated before in my presentation in October 2024, while the situation in our laboratory is not exactly critical when compared to most faculties there is still much room for improvement:

- The data is still being recorded with pen and paper;
- Old software and data is often lost in archive - for instance setup executables with old machine control software are stored on non-inventoried DVD's;
- Old machines (mostly PC's) tend to break - and their fault points are very frequently the hard-drives (loss of data);
- The single researcher is "unreliable", meaning that on average they won't mind about keeping a certain standard if this standard is not enforced via software, or they will forget to notify the others when an instrument is down for fault or maintenance;
- Most control software is proprietary - and outputs proprietary files.

Another issue arose right at the beginning of the development of the software in object and persists to this day, that is the difficulty and almost

impossibility to automatically parse and store metadata regarding samples, experiments or just instrument logs: this data taken in its primitive raw form is chaotic and of little to no use to any researcher other than the person that had been using the instrument in that particular time frame as raw logs for the most part only contain timestamps followed by unitless readings of sensors - temperature, pressure, humidity etc. - which in turn also vary from one instrument to the other, if for instance their sensors are located at different ranges from the sample that is being produced or analysed, or if those sensors are calibrated differently. The intent of this project is not to act upon this issue, leaving to the single researcher the freedom of filtering and selecting autonomously the data relevant to their experiment - and eventually upload the parsed logs to the eLN for post-processing.

1.1.2 The XPS incident

The climax of these shortcomings has resulted in the incident of August 2024 where our XPS spectrometer went down for more than a month because the main drive of the PC - an old 20 GB IDE HDD - died suddenly preventing boot to Windows and backup to another drive.

- The control software installed on the machine was closed-source, only available on Windows XP and only compatible with the PCI acquisition card provided by the company, denying any possibility of upgrading just the measurement station leaving the old instrument operational.
- The installer for the control software has been lost as no DVD was to be found in the laboratory and even the author of the software could not be of much help as «nobody present today in our company still really knows the details and secrets» - to use their words.
- The smartctl analysis showed a record of 115'000 power on hours - equivalent to roughly 13 years of non-stop activity - a raw error rate in the 9000's and two reallocated sectors, in short all synonyms of a terminal hard drive.
- No compatible replacement drive was immediately available; no IDE to SATA/USB interface was available either.
- The 20-year old processor - Intel Celeron Northwood 128 - had a 32-bit architecture and could not run most modern OS'; all rescue operations have been done through Damn Small Linux 2024.

Figure 1.1: Screenshot of the SMART status of the drive in the XPS computer, read through DSL 2024’s terminal.

- No backup of the computer’s data was available anywhere.
- The entire setup was undocumented - meaning no user manuals, no cable maps, no troubleshoot documentation and not even inventory labels/entries were available.

As a more accustomed reader might have guessed all of these problems could’ve been avoided with progressive part upgrades over the years (especially regarding the OS since Windows XP has been EOL for over a decade and should not be granted access to the internet) a good disaster recovery plan or just updated documentation on PC’s, peripherals, cables and more. Following precisely the Swiss cheese model these individually small negligences summed together have held back the reinstatement of the instrument for over a month.

1.1.3 The Data Management Plan

A LDMP - **Laboratory Data Management Plan** - has been produced by our group on February 2025 with details on data collection, licensing and management for just the **PLD-MODA** instrument. What follows is an extremely abridged version of the original document.

Administrative information

Technique: Pulsed Laser Deposition.

Status: Operative.

Placed in: CNR-SPIN Naples - MODA laboratory, to be moved to the new NFFA-DI lab.

Software deployed: TSST Pulsed Laser Deposition System Control v4.13 (proprietary).

Ancillary equipment: *In-situ High-Pressure RHEED* - a differential pumping system allows the use of RHEED for growth pressure up to few 10^{-1} mbar; software deployed: *kSA 400*.

Instrument scientist: [Fabio Miletto Granozio](#)

Data curator: [Alessia Sambri](#)

Data and Metadata Collection

Raw data file format: The PLD itself only produces a small amount of raw data all in plain text with comma/blank-space separated variables - so it can also be analysed as a csv; the RHEED is capable of producing logs in txt and csv formats, pictures in bmp, png and other image formats, and stores the data from the original readings in a proprietary format (*.ksah*).

Average amount of data produced in 8 hours: PLD raw logs don't usually exceed 2 MB; RHEED output is highly dependant on activity, with a volume ranging from less than a MB when idle to around 30 MB (per 8 hours) in full activity. Typically test sessions only last around 60 minutes - averaging a data rate of ~ 4 MB/h.

Metadata collection: the ensuing practices are followed:

- Not all logs from the machines are preserved, and the remaining data is heavily parsed to a few kilobytes at worst.
- There's currently no collection of additional metadata by an open source laboratory notebook, although eLabFTW has been proposed and is being tested - which is the entire point of the present document.
- No well defined standard is currently enforced to name our samples, but a commonly accepted nomenclature is a unique code formatted as NA-25-001, where NA is the location of the lab, 25 is the year in ISO %y format and 001 is a unique incremental identifier to be reset at the end of the year (see section [2.1](#)).

- We use a well defined metadata schema and format: during every experiment we collect date and name of sample, followed by short recipe of the material with intermediate steps and measurements.

Publication phase

Data and metadata publication:

- Publication of data and related metadata on open and trusted repository with a d.o.i. will only occur if required by the publishing journal.
- It is still unknown how published processed data and metadata will be licensed.

Scientific publication:

- After being peer reviewed, most of the scientific publications will be at least uploaded on an open access repository such as Zenodo (yet to decide).
- All the publications will report in their metadata the d.o.i. of the related data and metadata if published.
- It is still unknown if any scientific output related to data such as presentation or posters will be open access registered with a d.o.i. and licensed (if published).

Data and metadata storage and preservation

Still to be discussed. Most likely an external NAS will be used for daily backups of the computers but no relevant data should ever be left as a unique copy on the machines since no parsing will be done on the instruments' raw logs, and automatic classification and cataloguing of the instruments' outputs are next to impossible - as stated previously.

1.2 Enter eLabFTW

The eLN chosen taking into account simplicity, usability, security and easiness of setup, maintenance and backup was **eLabFTW**, a completely free and open source eLN which:

- Provides a clean, user-friendly interface for the researcher to interact with;

- Is designed by researchers, which is evident in the way it manages resources and experiments;
- Can be used as inventory of samples, batches, instruments and sample positions, and to keep track of instrument maintenance;
- Is widely backed up by a large community of contributors who have been improving the software for more than a decade not just with programming but also by testing, donating and replying to new users in the GitHub Issues.

The code is available for download on GitHub and the installation on server can be managed through Docker. The software is licenced under AGPL which binds any derivative works under compatible open-source licenses. The project's official website is elabftw.net.

1.2.1 eLabFTW's entities

As documented in the official eLabFTW user guide¹: «There are two main entities (objects) types: *Experiments* and *Resources*.» One is owned by a user, the other by a team, one describes an experiment, the other an item or asset of our laboratory. Note that from now on names of eLabFTW entries, assets and objects in general will be referred to using capitalized words to avoid confusion with other uses of those terms.

Experiments are the core feature of eLabFTW (or any good eLN for the matter) and can be used to contain and process recipes, deposition conditions and other pieces of information regarding the creation, analysis and storage of a sample. They are assigned their own ID's by eLab and they can be created from a database mask called **Template** which also associates the entry to a specific **Category** - with its own ID on eLab. Note that Templates and Categories are also available for Resources, although they are handled separately by the software.

Resources (or **Items**) are the entries which best suit our objectives for samples, instruments and substrates management as they're optimized to contain information about assets available in the laboratory and can be assigned to an entire team rather than a single person. They too are assigned their own ID's by eLab and they too can be created from a Template and assigned to a Category.

¹Source: eLabFTW User Guide for v5.1.15 - [archived on the Wayback Machine on 20/03/2025](https://www.waybackmachine.org/web/2020032025032025/eLabFTW%20User%20Guide%20for%20v5.1.15/).^[1]

Different entities can also be linked together for many reasons: for instance it's possible to bind a sample (Item) to an Experiment revolving around it, or a sample to the substrates batch from which its substrate is taken - since they are both Items; a symlink (which eLab calls **item link**) is created on both entries on eLab's website for easy access to one from the other, and behind the scenes some important data of one entry is written into the other and vice versa - which simplifies getting informations on linked items from the API. Last but not least it's also possible to upload a file on eLabFTW as an attachment to an Experiment or Resource, which is something I have included in AMORE too.

1.2.2 eLabFTW's API endpoints

eLabFTW's **REST API v2** adheres to modern web standards, utilizing HTTP methods GET, POST, PATCH and DELETE for *CRUD* (acronym of "Create, Read, Update and Delete") operations and returning JSON responses. The API follows **REST** principles with resource-centric endpoints (like `/experiments` and `/items`, see below) and conventional status codes.

Authentication for the API relies on **API keys** which users generate in their settings panel (see section 4.1). Unlike standard web authentication API keys bypass MFA checks as they are treated as stand-alone credentials with predefined permissions: this comes in handy later when talking about the importance of proper key storage (section 3.3.5); every time a new key is created **its permission** must be set - either read-only or read/write - and even if the key has write permissions they only apply to modifications of entries and options within the user's domain, set by the administrator and dependant on the user's team; an API key is only shown once, then encrypted forever and stored in the database.

Most general endpoints (like `/experiments` and `/items`) behave this way:

- GET requests directed to the endpoint will download a JSON with summarized data and metadata about the 15 most recent experiments;
- GET requests to the endpoint can be used to lookup specific entries by appending a search query to the endpoint's URL² - for instance

²eLabFTW GitHub Issue #4838: "Where is the syntax of (advanced) queries documented?".[2]

adding "?limit=9999" will extend the number of results shown to a maximum value of 9999;

- POST requests directed to the endpoint will result in the creation of a new resource with the parameters specified in the payload;
- The API includes **resource-specific** endpoints where the resource is identified by ID (for instance `/items/123`) and **action-specific** endpoints (like `/experiments/456/timestamps`) for non-CRUD functions;
- PATCH and DELETE requests to a resource-specific endpoint can be used to respectively update and delete said resource;
- POST requests to a resource-specific endpoint will duplicate it;
- The API key and *Content-Type* must be specified inside the header of every request - with few exceptions.

The API endpoint for managing a Resource (`/api/v2/items/{id}`) allows CRUD operations on Resources almost identical to those allowed for the Experiments, with the only exception being a difference in behaviour of the Item creation endpoint due to a bug of versions 5.1.15 and previous[3]: values for body, metadata, rating and possibly more fields cannot be provided during Item creation but only through patching at a later instant. This issue forced me to push most of the data provided by the user during sample creation (especially metadata which contains the most important data for samples as seen later) through *patching of the sample created immediately before* - which means three requests are made to eLab instead of just a single POST request:

- POST to `/items` endpoint to initialize the eLab Item with title, tags and ID of the Category the new sample;
- GET to the same endpoint to recover the ID of the newly created Item;
- PATCH to the resource-specific endpoint of the newly created Item to add body and metadata.

Action-specific endpoints can be used to upload files, link items, verify a user's identity etc. For instance the endpoint to attach a file to an Item is `/items/135/uploads`, which accepts POST and GET requests, and every upload has its own resource-specific endpoint (`/items/135/uploads/1`) which accepts PATCH, GET and DELETE requests.

1.3 Data stream pipeline

1.3.1 Theorized pipeline

As presented in October the original pipeline was a circular stream of data exchanged between the research team, the instruments, the eLN and the tangent data stream to OFED (figure 1.2).

- The researcher would grab a substrate from a certain available batch, deposit material on it, then add a new entry for that sample on eLabFTW.
- Output logs, images and other machine acquisitions would be sent to a certain piece of software developed specifically for parsing by the other members of our team.
- The data processed by this software would be transferred towards OFED's machines in Trieste, but also towards our own eLN.
- Results harvested by the scientists and data parsed by the other software would be taken in by another software - developed by me - further processed and safely stored on eLabFTW where the researchers could edit, share and easily recover this data, complying with the FAIR principles.

Additionally the pipeline would include reliable **backup** and **disaster recovery** methods to preserve the continuity and the database of our eLN and some server application like **NetBox** to keep an inventory of the instruments, the computers, the acquisition cards and other assets - complete with cable mapping and maintenance/malfunctions warnings. Alternatively **snipeit** and **homebox** were considered too, renouncing cable/LAN mapping and other features in favour of an easier setup and a much lighter user experience.

1.3.2 Expected pipeline

Another more realistic pipeline presented in October already focused more on the main data stream rather than the auxiliary services (backup, inventory, etc.). This pipeline would revolve entirely around my software.

- The researcher would grab a substrate from a certain available batch, deposit material on it, process it, analyse it, write down the results on the GUI I've developed.

Figure 1.2: Graphical visualization of the original pipeline.

Figure 1.3: Graphical visualization of the realistic pipeline.

- Output logs, images and other machine acquisitions would be acquired automatically (or on demand) by my software on every run of the instruments.
- Results fed into my software would be further processed and pushed to eLabFTW where the researchers could edit, share and easily recover this data, complying with the FAIR principles.
- Informations requested from eLab would be kept to a minimum, making the data exchange between my software and eLabFTW mostly unidirectional.

1.3.3 Actual pipeline

The biggest change from the ideal pipeline in the actualization of this scheme is the complete lack (at the time) of a proper disaster recovery solution and an consultable (searchable and accessible) backup of eLab's database: the virtual machine on which eLabFTW is currently running in our servers - and not the database or single entries - is backed up every night with a retaining policy of 5 daily, 2 weekly and 2 monthly backups, all stored in a separate NAS. This solution doesn't allow for quick access to the data saved in the archives since it copies the entire image of the VM rather than just eLab's database; for the same reason it doesn't allow to restore entries and settings selectively meaning that if for some reason an important experiment is altered in an unrecoverable way - which is hard to do since eLab keeps track of the edits made on an entry - it cannot be immediately restored from backup without permanently losing any other modification made since the last backup operation.

Other than that the inventory is now managed directly on eLabFTW, signalling downtimes and keeping track of maintenance directly on the eLN; no cable mapping has been done.

- The researcher grabs a substrate from a certain available batch, deposits material on it, processes and analyses it, writes down the results on the GUI I've developed - attaching files up to 100 MB if required.
- Results fed into my software are further processed and pushed to eLabFTW where the researchers can edit, share and easily recover this data, complying with the FAIR principles; the same software enforces a series of standards best described later (chapter 2).

- Output logs, images and other machine acquisitions are either processed by the scientist and uploaded as attachments or analysed by my colleagues' applications and NOMAD plug-ins for additional processing and transferring to OFED.
- eLabFTW and my software exchange data bidirectionally and constantly, with GET requests to eLab more frequent than POST, PATCH and DELETE requests combined.

Chapter 2

Defining a standard for our eLabFTW

The importance of defining a standard upfront didn't become immediately clear, as the main issues only arose after the first few weeks of work: for starters no guidelines were defined for naming sectors, slots and holders - the positions inside every instrument where a sample could be placed - for digital sample tracking, plus no official digital inventory of the laboratory has ever been produced before, and it's easy to imagine how these two elements alone impacted negatively on the time required for this project.

Even if it's true - with the benefit of hindsight - that the standard should have been fully defined before starting the development of my software (AMORE), issues of incompatibility between the few provided starting guidelines and what was actually possible with eLabFTW's API were only discovered during development: for instance, eLab has no way to validate our internal standard ID for samples in a manner which forbids non-admin users (scientists) from breaking said standard; it also doesn't allow username and password login when accessing the database through API¹, which means the scientists have to carry their own API key everywhere to access eLab through AMORE (BYOK system). Other than that, changes between both minor and major version updates of eLabFTW posed another threat to AMORE's development since the API endpoint's behaviour

¹eLabFTW GitHub Issue [#5543](#): "Login via API using Username, PW and eventual MFA".[4]

Figure 2.1: Flowchart of the ideal workflow when realizing a third-party client for an eLN (oriented horizontally to save space).

would sometimes change drastically^{2 3}.

The actual workflow started by clarifying the platform (eLN) to be used and the final objectives, and every subsequent step has been decided situationally: whenever a new problem rose the code was adjusted to circumvent it. A better way to structure our workflow would have been studying the documentation for the API in depth, then agree on a common standard, then figure out what’s possible and what isn’t and only after creating a standard which is completely possible to implement through eLab’s API we should’ve started development.

What follows is an in-depth explanation of the standard adopted for the names of the samples and those of the positions, plus the methods used to implement said standard into our eLabFTW instance. Note that the standard has been agreed upon by the head scientist and part of the team of MODA laboratory, and is to be followed religiously by scientists and data curators.

2.1 Nomenclature

Since one of the core features requested for AMORE was sample tracking, we first had to decide on how to identify both samples and their locations through univocal ID’s (not necessarily equivalent to, but not unlike

²eLabFTW GitHub Issue #5480: “[API Items endpoint] New / i t e m s can’t be provided with preset "body", "metadata" and "rating" via curl”.[3]

³eLabFTW GitHub Issue #5577: “Permission inconsistency between eLabFTW’s web interface and API endpoint / i t e m s / i d where even GET calls return 403 on item everyone is allowed to read”.[5]

database primary keys) formatted in a "human-readable" style, acting both as names or titles, and ID's. An internal standard nomenclature system for samples - which I will refer to as **Standard ID** or **STD-ID** from now on - was already adopted unofficially (not enforced) inside the laboratory since data about the materials produced was (naturally) already being harvested and catalogued by the scientists on both the lab computers and their personal devices.

While the same was true for the names of the positions, in their case there was little consistency between different instruments, included but not limited to the use of different separator characters between the name of the instrument and that of the sector (-, -, white spaces etc.) or the presence of other special characters. We later decided on how to handle sample tracking on eLabFTW, adopting a method which - as explained in detail later - uses **position names** (strings) as primary keys to identify slots on eLab; if that is the case, then these strings must absolutely follow a well defined scheme religiously, and if one position is deleted erroneously from eLab's database there must be a way to immediately restore it.

2.1.1 Standard ID for samples

The "name" used to identify a sample internally must contain info on the faculty in which it has been created, the year of deposition/creation and a progressive univocal numerical ID. All of these informations must be included in the first 9 characters of every sample's title on eLabFTW and constitute the sample's own **Standard ID**. The name of the sample - which is usually the chemical composition of the material created - must always follow the Standard ID, from which it must always be separated by a hyphen-minus character (Unicode U+002D) enclosed between two white spaces (" - "). While this rule is enforced by AMORE - whose main purpose is generating and handling exactly the STD-ID's of new and old samples - it is critical that every scientist who has access to our eLabFTW database and wishes to change the name of a pre-existent sample, or create a new one directly on eLab bypassing AMORE, always follows the previous instructions to ensure that the client visualizes and handles every sample correctly.

Na-25-000 - STO LAO...

Example of a full title for a sample in our eLabFTW.

The Standard ID must be made up of three sections, separated by a hyphen-minus character (Unicode U+002D) with no white spaces in-between. Its length must be exactly 9 characters - of which indexes 2 and 5 are hyphens.

- First two characters (indexes 0 and 1) refer to **the location of the faculty** where the sample has been created - similarly to province codes in Italy; as explained later AMORE will default it to "Na" (Naples) for practical reasons, and only cities hosting a CNR-SPIN faculty can be selected in the drop-down menu by default.
- The second pair of characters (indexes 3 and 4) is just **the year of deposition/creation** of the sample in two digit format (%y).
- The last segment (indexes 6 through 8) is **the sample's univocal ID**, which is assigned progressively to new samples, is reset to 001 at the beginning of the year and caps (hypothetically) at 999.

Since the almost totality of samples to be added to eLabFTW through AMORE have been or will be created in Naples, another way to refer univocally to one of our materials could be a 5-digit integer made of just the last two sections - which are the two digit year and the progressive ID (25001, 25002...). The advantages of using such method are:

- Both the year and the ID can be recovered immediately, as the former is the integer result of division between this number and 10'000 (Python operator //), while the latter is the remainder of the same operation (Python operator %);
- As a consequence it's also easier to get the latest unique ID and generate the next one;
- It's easier to validate on both client and server side;
- It can serve as a primary key.

The main disadvantage is that this method doesn't keep track of the location where the sample has been manufactured, it's less recognizable since eLab uses its own integer ID's and it's generally less elegant. Taking pros and cons into account we decided to adopt both standards: the first Standard ID is shown at the beginning of the sample's title on eLab while the **Integer ID** is kept as extra metadata field ("STD-ID") inside the resource entry on eLab.

2.1.2 Titles of the positions/slots on eLabFTW

A second problem which came out much later was assigning a proper name to every sample position inside our instruments. To clarify, a **sample position** is an area inside our laboratory designed to hold a sample either for storage, for manufacturing or processing, for analysis or for moving it between different instruments. Depending on their purposes, sample positions can be said to be located:

- In an **instrument** if the sample contained in it is subject to a process or characterization;
- In a **chamber** if their purpose is just the temporary storage of a sample (holding, moving...);
- In an **inventory** if their purpose is the permanent storage of old or dismissed samples.

The umbrella term chosen to refer to all of these cases is **instrument** since differentiating between these terms was pointless in the context of developing AMORE. The single sample positions inside every instrument will be referred to as **slots**. Larger instruments containing so many slots that listing every slot under a single group would be impractical, a division in groups called **sectors** is applied; where no sector is specified, we assume that the instrument only has one "Main" sector plus a "LOST" one (see below).

A slot is considered **available** or empty if it isn't currently occupied by any sample. Since the position name is expected to be used as a primary key for sample location and movement, this name must identify univocally the slot it's referred to and contain informations on its instrument (and eventually its sector) of belonging. For this purpose, the following standard nomenclature is proposed:

INST - Slot *or* INST - Sec - Slot

Scheme of a title for a sample position in our eLabFTW; left: for smaller instruments without sectors; right: for bigger instruments divided in sectors.

- Block **INST** is a 3-4 characters-long string (an acronym or any sort of abbreviation) representing the **instrument**; while technically not bound to the 4 character limit it's highly suggested to keep it as short as possible.

- Block **Slot** is the name of the slot with no defined character limit.
- Block **Sec** is a 4 or less characters-long string representing the **sector** of the instrument.
- INST, Sec and Slot can consist of any combination of letters and digits, as long as it's understandable for the scientists.
- None of the three blocks should contain special characters and absolutely must not contain white spaces or hyphen symbols (Unicode U+002D, U+2010, U+2011, U+2212, U+2013 or U+2014) as these characters are used as separators to identify instrument, sector and slot of the position.
- A hyphen-minus character (Unicode U+002D) enclosed between two white spaces (" - ") must be used as a separator between the three blocks.

Special cases of sample positions are the **LOST sectors**, areas of our instruments - inaccessible for the vast majority of the time - where samples are occasionally dropped by mistake, after which they are considered lost and unrecoverable; although in reality the resources can be physically recovered during extraordinary maintenance, by that time its creator has already moved forward to the next sample, or the lost sample has simply broken as a consequence of the drop. Usually, no more than two to four samples per instrument are lost every year.

2.2 Implementation inside eLabFTW

After the standard is defined and agreed upon by the scientists our eLabFTW instance is to be modified with some additions in terms of defining templates, creating the first experiments and items, and generally implement the accepted standard through these resources, with the objective of creating exactly what our team had in mind for an eLN.

The problems mentioned at the beginning of chapter 2 are also caused by incompatibilities between our objectives and the capabilities of eLab's API, and agreeing on a common language - in more ways than one - is not sufficient to solve these issues. Specifically, we had to follow a few important steps in order to "terraform" the server to pursue our objectives.

- Creating a Template for an eLab Experiment named "**Sample Locator**" which would later serve as a base for the sample tracker feature.

- Creating the following Item Categories, with these exact names:
 - **Sample:** Template for new samples pre-loaded with useful metadata fields about ownership, position, substrate batch used, proposal associated, etc.;
 - **Substrates Batch:** Template for substrates batches, which are "sets" of base material on which deposition is done, pre-loaded with metadata like size, type of compound (see below) and name of the supplier;
 - **Proposal:** Template for proposals to manage contributions from external users;
 - **Compound:** Template for substrate compounds, not directly relevant in the development of AMORE;
 - **Process Instrument and Measurement Instrument:** Templates for instruments, not relevant in the development of AMORE but incredibly useful to keep track of maintenance, downtime, damages and other events regarding our instruments;
- Creating Templates for other eLabFTW Experiments - not relevant to the development of AMORE.
- Creating the accounts of the scientists and allocate every scientist into one or more teams.

2.2.1 Items/Resources

Items created all fall within one of the Categories listed at the beginning of this section. In reality the Items created by AMORE only belong to the "*Sample*" Category and are only linked to proposals and substrates batches, which leaves the other categories out of the picture; no operation (POST or PATCH request) is ever done towards Items of the "Proposal" Category - which means AMORE only alters samples and substrates batches.

Sample Items must contain basic and for the most part immutable informations about the samples created in our laboratories, the first and most important of which is the **Title** field which must consist of the Standard ID of the sample followed by its name - usually the chemical composition of the material - separated by a hyphen-minus enclosed between two white spaces as stated before. The metadata section of every sample always contains the following fields:

- **Owner:** ID and name of eLabFTW user who owns the sample and is responsible for it;
- **STD-ID:** Integer ID of the sample (e.g. 25001, 25002...);
- **Position:** string with the full name of the slot currently containing the sample - which can be patched by AMORE's sample tracker;
- **Proposal:** ID (Item) of the proposal associated to the sample;
- **Substrates Batch:** ID (Item) of the substrates batch from which the sample's substrate is taken;
- **Substrates Holder:** string containing the name or number of the substrate holder currently sustaining the sample - which at present is not represented by an Item Category on eLab.

Substrates Batch Items must contain basic informations about the batches of substrates available (or depleted) in our laboratories; most informations stored are immutable, with the sole exception of the value of the field "*Available pieces*". The **Title** field must contain the number of the batch and the names of the base material and the supplier (e.g. "*Batch n.3245 STO from Crystec*"); no naming standard is currently enforced. The metadata section must always contain the following fields:

- **Compound:** ID of the base compound, which is an Item of Category "Compound";
- **Size:** string containing the form factor in free format (e.g. "*5 mm x 5 mm*", "*10 mm sq*", "*2 in circ.*", etc.);
- **Orientation:** string containing the orientation in free format (e.g. "*(001)*");
- **Supplier:** string containing name of the supplier;
- **Purchased by:** string with the full name of the scientist who requested the purchase;
- **Surface treatment:** brief description of the treatments the substrates have been subjected to;
- **Available pieces:** integer number of available pieces left inside the batch before it's depleted - the only value that changes regularly.

2.2.2 The Sample Locator Experiment

Initially every slot was represented on eLab by its own Item flagged into the "Sample Position" Category. The idea was linking the contained Sample to this Resource, so upon inspection of either the sample or the position asset one could easily assess which sample was associated with a certain slot or vice versa, or generally if a slot was available or occupied, or if a sample was allocated, dismissed or lost. We then realized that requesting eLabFTW for no less than 30 to 40 assets all in separate requests and having to wait around 8 to 10 seconds *on every refresh of the page* for the software to download all of it, store it in memory and parse it was not the fastest, the most bandwidth/power-efficient or generally the smartest idea.

After weeks of trial and error we decided instead of using a single entry on eLabFTW - specifically an Experiment - to serve as a **Sample Locator**. Using eLab's metadata field for experiments we've created a Template with the standard name of every slot of every instrument in our laboratory used as univocal key for the Locator's **extra fields**, whose type would be set to "item" and whose value would be either null, empty string or the eLab-ID of a Resource present in that specific slot. The slots are divided in **groups**, whose names are set equal to the extended full names of our instruments - rather than just their abbreviations ("PLD MODA" instead of "PLD1", etc.).

Of course even this approach has its disadvantages which I have always taken into consideration during development of AMORE:

- Every scientist must have writing permissions on a single Experiment whose careless tampering could result in severe loss of data;
- Extra fields are exceptionally hard to work on since metadata in eLabFTW is handled in a huge single-line string containing a JSON object nested to multiple levels; removing an Item from inside a metadata field is hard to do through the API and practically impossible to do via the web interface - at least without deleting the entire field (slot) together with the Sample;
- Linking (and unlinking) Items through the API is not an automatic process and if not done properly could result in various errors;
- eLabFTW's fields which take an ID of another Resource or Experiment as value **accept integers, strings and NoneTypes** without any sort of validation - as long as it contains a number it will show an

entry, regardless of the type of the value (which is especially weird considering that most of eLab's backend is programmed either in PHP or TypeScript, perhaps JavaScript is to blame).

Last but not least the title of the Experiment must be exactly "*Sample Locator*" since AMORE only downloads data from the first Experiment it finds whose name is an exact match.

Figure 2.2: Screenshot of the Sample Locator Experiment on our eLabFTW. Notice that the extra fields are divided in groups named after the instrument they belong to; behind the scenes the extra fields are all on the same level and under the same JSON key, therefore their names must be unique.

Chapter 3

Introducing AMORE: basic standard sample management

AMORE - short for "**A**utonomous **M**anagement of **O**utputs for **R**esearch **E**fficiency" - is a minimal GUI (*Graphical User Interface*) developed to assist the transition between the physical paper laboratory notebook to our own eLN of choice - eLabFTW. It can be said that most of the codebase has been written exclusively with our nomenclature standard and eLabFTW setup (chapters 2.1 and 2.2 respectively) in mind.

3.1 What is AMORE?

The acronym AMORE was chosen thinking of my fiancée; since her actual first name is made up of two words of length 5 and 8 characters respectively you can see how it would've been impractical to call the software "MARIA GIOVANNA" and then form a sentence with those 13 letters, or alternatively to form a good acronym with the word "MARYLOU" - her nickname.

The software serves as a minimal client for our scientists to interact with, in order to add new samples to eLab and move any pre-existing sample from one position to the other (sample tracking). It's back-end is developed entirely in **Python3** (specifically on Python 3.12 - with only very few limits to retro-compatibility) with usage of built-in modules *os*, *sys*, *json*, *datetime* mainly plus additional modules *requests*, *flask* and *dotenv* (development only). The front-end is developed in HTML5 and CSS, and its contents are generated with the web framework **Flask** - also programmed in Python - through the use of template engine *Jinja*. To enable pop-up

windows (used to flash user warnings, errors, success messages and substrates batches status messages) a total of 27 lines of JavaScript code (minus empty lines) have been generated by open-source LLM DeepSeek-R1.

The authentication to eLabFTW is made via a personal API key which must be provided by the user on every login; after the login the key is encrypted and stored in a session cookie which expires after 10 minutes of inactivity or upon (AMORE's) server restart.

The software only stores immutable data, which it downloads automatically from the source (eLabFTW) via a dedicated script (described in section 5.4.3), in JSON dictionaries located in the var module (section 5.3). Technically speaking the software approach towards data storage is object-oriented (OODB).

3.1.1 Public repository and license

The source code of AMORE is entirely public and available:

- On the general GitHub repository of the MDMC ([Master-Data-Management-and-Curation/Thesis_Code](#)) under the folder `cnr-spin.na`;
- On my personal GitHub account ([PioApocalypse/AMORE](#)).

The repository is articulated on two branches: a *main* branch and a *dev* branch, where the former is only updated to the latest tested and working commit while the latter contains anything experimental (new features, modules substitutions, untested modifications, etc.). A new release is published any time a major feature is introduced or some really small but crucial error is fixed; versioning is done following the *Pride Versioning 0.3.0* standard: `PROUD.DEFAULT.SHAME` - where `PROUD` is the number to increase when a major update is released, `DEFAULT` is to be increased on normal/okay releases and `SHAME` is the number to bump when «*fixing things too embarrassing to admit*». ¹

License The first few versions of AMORE were published under GPLv3, later changed to MIT for less legal complexity, uniformity with jQuery's and DataTables' licenses (both under MIT), and generally because we've felt no need to keep a more restrictive license for a piece of software which already has an extremely narrow field of application.

¹Pride Versioning 0.3.0 - pridever.org

MIT license allows everyone to use, modify, distribute and sublicense AMORE for any purpose - including contributions to proprietary code - with the only restriction being that the user must always include the original copyright notice and license in all copies; additionally no warranty or liability is provided by the author. While very similar to Apache 2.0 license, MIT offers no patent/copyleft protection which - again - was not deemed necessary for this use case.

Note that since the software relies heavily on JSON objects it must also comply with the JSON licence, therefore it «Shall be used for Good, not Evil»².

3.2 Why is AMORE

Starting from the situation described in chapter 1, the main objective of AMORE - its *raison d'être* - is to encourage and facilitate the transition from the physical paper laboratory notebook to our eLN of choice, presenting the scientists with a minimal user interface to interact with for quickly prompting and recovering all available informations on a certain sample. To achieve this one objective the interface must, despite its minimal appearance:

- Allow the users to create a new sample on eLabFTW complete with every essential data;
- Allow the users to quickly keep track of the position of every sample in the laboratory;
- Allow the users to move a pre-existing sample around;
- Minimise user errors during sample/experiment submissions or while editing or moving around a resource;
- Keep track of who creates/edits what through a login system (allowing authentication and blame);
- Export experiment or sample data (JSON) on demand.

The last item on the list is especially important if contextualized within our pipeline, since by allowing on-demand data export we can facilitate the acquisition of already processed data for NeXus conversion.

²The JSON license: <https://json.org/license.html>

An additional objective I wanted to pursue personally was to develop AMORE using the lowest number of dependencies possible, since there is a high risk that the software won't be maintained and upgraded after my contract is due and I desire to keep it far from falling into dependency hell at all costs. For this reason the only Python libraries required to install AMORE on server without Docker are *requests* and *Flask*, leaving out even eLabFTW's own Python library.

3.3 Setup of AMORE on server

There are mainly three ways of installing AMORE on a server without any advanced dedicated web server software (like Apache HTTP or nginx):

1. Through the installation wizard;
2. Via dockerfile;
3. Manual install.

3.3.1 System requirements

AMORE has been tested on very elementary virtual machines - 1 core and 1 GB of RAM each. Since we do not plan on exposing the service to the internet, the average expected concurrent sessions are no more than two; it is safe to assume that any machine produced after the millennium bug is powerful enough to handle this software without issues or lag of any kind - despite the codebase being written for two thirds in Python.

The software requirements are better defined. First of all it is crucial that the server is hosted on a Linux distribution, preferably but not necessarily one with Systemd as init system; Almalinux/Rocky Linux 9, Linux Mint 22, Ubuntu Server 24 and Nobara Linux 41 have all been tested. Installing through Docker obviously requires **Docker** to be installed and enabled on the machine, and if the administrator decides to install AMORE via its own installation script **Bash 5**, library **python-requests** and Unix binary **cURL** are also required. As mentioned before AMORE itself only requires Python libraries **requests** and **Flask**.

3.3.2 Installation wizard and dockerfile

The contents of the installation wizard (**setup.sh**) are illustrated in detail in section 5.4.1. The script is very rudimentary and guides the user

through the installation process, during which it requires the base URL of the eLabFTW instance and a valid API key for downloading and caching some important data (see section 3.3.4); it also asks the user if any requests to the eLabFTW server should require SSL verification (HTTPS-only) or not - option only really useful if the eLab instance has a self-signed certificate.

By default the wizard is agnostic to the format of the provided URL, which means that the administrator can either include or omit both the protocol prefix (`http://`, `https://...`) and the trailing slash at the end of the URL, although they cannot omit non-default port numbers meaning that if the instance is exposed through a port different than 80 or 443 the base URL must also state the port number (e.g. if eLabFTW is exposed through port 8080: `http://demo.elabftw.net:8080/`). After getting the URL from the admin the script will scan it for a valid eLabFTW instance; if not found it will prompt the user again, unless the `--force` flag is specified.

Flags The installation script also recognizes the following options:

- `--force`: Disables URL check for valid eLabFTW instance;
- `--literal`: Disables URL normalization, which means the user must specify both protocol prefix and trailing slash while prompting the URL;
- `--quick`: Removes pauses between instructions;
- `--file`: Looks for environmental variables in file `./config.json` before attempting installation; if not all required variables are specified the user will still be prompted for those - with the exception of variable `HOST_PORT` which will be defaulted to 5000; invalid variables in `./config.json` are simply ignored by the wizard; the list of every supported variable is present in a `./config.json.example` file in the root folder of AMORE.

After receiving input from the user the script checks if Docker is properly installed and enabled; it then builds the Docker image *amore* and runs it into a dedicated container named "*amore-container*", forwarding the container port 5000 (Flask) to the host port of choice (or 5000 by default).

Note that, in order not to leave a copy in clear of the API key used for the setup, the `config.json` file will be deleted after installation even if Docker fails to build or run the image.

3.3.3 Manual install

Alternatively to using the dockerfile AMORE can also be easily installed manually thanks to its development's "near-zero dependency" policy. While less suited for production mainly for security reasons, it's a great method for testing the software on the go without having to rebuild the entire Docker image. Other than making sure the Python requirements are met the user must create its own virtual environment, export the variables needed by the software and run the script *scan_elab.py* before attempting to start the Flask server.

The virtual environment can be created via Python module *venv* directly into the cloned AMORE root folder, and although it's discouraged it's possible to have the virtual environment automatically export the variables necessary for AMORE's operativity by appending the following lines to the venv activator script:

```
export PYTHONPATH="/full/path/to/AMORE/"
export ELABFTW_BASE_URL="https://elabftw.mydomain.net/"
export VERIFY_SSL=True
```

After activating the virtual environment via *source*, the requirements can be installed via PIP, either manually or using the *requirements.txt* file in AMORE's root folder. At this point the *scan_elab.py* script can be run, and if the success message are printed the Flask server can be activated either via `python amore/gui/app.py` or by exporting the variable *FLASK_APP* to the path of the *app.py* file and running `flask run --host=0.0.0.0`.

3.3.4 Importing data from eLabFTW to avoid hard-coding

AMORE uses cache files in order to reduce both the back-end load and the number of requests made towards eLabFTW on every single page refresh. Besides the cache files generated automatically by Python, AMORE creates and reads two JSON objects stored in the *amore/var* folder.

- **categories.json** is a short, single-line object containing the names of all Items Categories present on the instance of eLabFTW (as key) and the ID's of each Category (as value). Since eLabFTW's API assigns a Category to a Resource only by ID - not by name - the creation of this file was necessary to eliminate the need for hard-coding the ID's of every Category of use in the request functions in our `client` file; another solution would've been raising a GET request to eLab's `items_types` endpoint every time a page refreshed which

would result in a bigger number of requests to eLab (proportional to the number of users) and also in a messier codebase since the JSON downloaded would have to be parsed every time to trim out unnecessary info.

To assure that everything works correctly, the administrator must first prepare the eLab instance by creating the Categories with the exact labels listed in section 2.2.

- **slots.json** is an indented list of dictionaries with names and short codes of every position's slot, sector and instrument/chamber of belonging. This file was needed to generate a single page for every slot in which the user could access all informations on availability of a slot and eventually on the contained sample.
Before generating this file the Experiment "Sample Locator" must be present on eLab - see subsection 2.2.2.

The main problems with cache files are that they become stale and then they're hard to invalidate. Since these informations are mostly immutable (not every day the laboratory acquires a new instrument) no automatic fetching is currently done by AMORE. The cache must be populated with the *scan_elab.py* script - which is done automatically by Docker during image building - and can be updated via the same script.

Note that *scan_elab.py* requires the requests library and reads the environmental variables ELABFTW_BASE_URL, API_KEY and VERIFY_SSL (see section 5.4.3).

3.3.5 The importance of secure key storage

The API key generated by the user which is to be used to authenticate via AMORE must be stored in a secure password manager or - if the user is really paranoid - on paper. It must never be stored in a non-encrypted txt file, especially if it also contains other informations that may help a malicious user trace the URL of the instance the key refers to (e.g. if the file's name is "elabftw spin unina.txt").

If a malicious agent were to gain access to a user's key it could easily do massive damage in very little time: for instance, a Bash script to loop through every Item on an eLabFTW instance sending a DELETE request via cURL could be as simple as this:

```
for i in {1..999}; do
    curl -H "Authorization: $API_KEY" -X DELETE \
        "https://elabftw.mysite.net/api/v2/items/$i"
done
```

Supposing every request takes 0.2 seconds - equivalent to a request rate of 5 req/s or 300 req/min - it would take a total of **3 minutes and 20 seconds** to delete 1000 database entries and **33 minutes** to delete 10'000; if the script in question starts from the highest (most recent) Item instead (for i in 999..1; do...) every eLab data on the newest 10 samples would be gone in just two seconds.

Backups might prove useful in this scenario but if the most recent backup is older than the most recent modifications pushed to eLab by the user there is loss of data, even if minimal. Also while eLabFTW does have a "soft delete" mechanism which makes resource deletion non-permanent, restoring an entry is no easy task, and it must be handled by the sysadmin since it's impossible to restore by GUI.³

³eLabFTW GitHub Issue [#4736](#): "Recovery/undelete functionality?"[6]

Chapter 4

Usage of AMORE

What follows is a brief user guide explaining AMORE's features without diving into its source code (seen in chapter 5). The chapter contains screenshots of the pages of the software. The default font used throughout the website is *Titillium Web*, widely adopted by many Italian PA services.

4.1 Login

After the server is operational, the user can reach AMORE through their web browser. The first page they will see is always the **login page**, due to the fact that every available route checks for the user's authentication and redirects to the login page if no valid session cookie is found.

The **API key** must be generated directly on eLabFTW: on ver. 5.1.15 under the *Account Settings* > *API KEYS* page it's possible to choose a name to identify the key - which is not important - and select the permission for the key.¹ Please be aware that AMORE only accepts API keys with both read and write permissions, and a specific pop-up error message will warn the user if the provided key doesn't have both permissions.

A generated key, encrypted with the *bcrypt algorithm*, is only shown by eLabFTW once - after which it must be safely stored by the user in a **proper password manager software**. The suggestion would be *KeePassXC* (or *KeePass2* for retro-compatibility); on the contrary, plain text files (txt) should never be used to store such information. eLab does not store un-encrypted generated keys but only their hashes, which it uses to verify if the key provided by the user is legit: this means that after the user closes

¹Source: eLabFTW User Guide for v5.1.15 - [archived on the Wayback Machine on 19/03/2025](#).^[7]

Figure 4.1: Screenshot of AMORE's login page.

the page with the key shown in clear there's no way to recover it anymore if it hasn't been copied elsewhere.

The login function will respond in one of two ways - authenticate the user or flash error. Error pop-ups have purple background (#7700ff) and will differentiate between generic error, invalid API key, read-only API key and log out attempt while session is expired.

Figure 4.2: Error messages flashed to the user on login screen after unsuccessful attempt.

If the key exists and is valid for writing operations the user is authenticated; a green pop-up message welcomes the user calling them by their full name (fetched from eLab): this is a way for the user to verify that the key they have used is in fact their own. The name of the user is also shown permanently on every page of the application. After the user is done with their work, a Log Out button will invalidate their session cookie, redirect-

ing the user back to the login page; the same effect is achieved by visiting the /logout route.

Since it's extremely common for a user to forget to log out from the client after the work is done, to prevent unauthorized access to AMORE the session cookie has a timeout of 10 minutes, starting from the latest user activity (refreshing a page resets the timer).

Figure 4.3: Screenshot of the index of AMORE ver. alpha-0.2.0.

4.2 Create Sample

Figure 4.4: Screenshot of route /create, where the user can add a new sample on eLab.

The main feature of AMORE is allowing the user to add a newly created sample on eLabFTW through a way more condensed form which prompts

for the essential informations needed to recognize a sample and position it inside the laboratory. The required fields are *Title*, *Position*, *Substrates Batch* and *Location*; optional fields are *Substrate Holder*, *Tags* (comma separated), *Proposal* and *Description*. Positions and Batches shown in the drop-down menu are all available, as AMORE filters out depleted batches and occupied slots; the Location field defaults to Naples since it's unlikely this software will be deployed elsewhere.

Attachments can be added either through drag-and-drop or by clicking the "*Browse...*" button; the maximum size for the entire payload is 100 MB, although on eLabFTW that is the size limit per file attached. Any file format is supported, and some formats (text and picture) can be opened directly in eLab.

After the submission of the form, the sample creation process begins. If errors occur they will be shown directly in a purple pop-up message, otherwise a green pop-up will state that the sample has been successfully created - printing the new Standard ID assigned to the sample.

4.2.1 Substrates batches status, remaining pieces

Although no standard naming convention has been defined for substrates batches, currently they are named as eLabFTW entries in a way which makes immediately clear what material the substrates are made of and who the supplier is (see section 2.2.1). This is especially important if we acknowledge that on the Sample Creation page the batches too are listed by name - no other info is shown directly to the user.

Another interesting aspect is that on sample creation AMORE also patches the Substrates Batch Item to reduce its number of available pieces by one, and it simultaneously checks if the number of pieces left in the batch is lower than 5 - in which case a yellow pop-up will be flashed to the user with the message «*Urgent: The batch {batch_name} is low on stock with {N} pieces left!*»; if the batch is completely empty a similar message on red background will be flashed and the batch in question is no longer selectable from the drop-down.

Although it's no easy task, knowing when a batch of substrates is low on (or out of) stock could allow for a series of improvements, like sending automatic warning e-mails to the purchaser.

4.3 Sample Tracker

AMORE for eLabFTW

Sample Tracker
Authenticated as Emanuele D'Amico

10 entries per page

Search:

Name	Instrument	Sector	Slot	Sample ID	Sample Name	Action
CART - 1	Cart	Main	1	Na-25-054	Prova	Move sample
CART - 2	Cart	Main	2	-	empty	Add new sample
CART - 3	Cart	Main	3	-	empty	Add new sample
CART - 4	Cart	Main	4	-	empty	Add new sample
CART - 5	Cart	Main	5	-	empty	Add new sample
CART - 6	Cart	Main	6	-	empty	Add new sample
CART - LA	Cart	Main	LA	-	empty	Add new sample
DIST - 1	Distribution Chamber	Main	1	-	empty	Add new sample
DIST - 10	Distribution Chamber	Main	10	-	empty	Add new sample
DIST - 2	Distribution Chamber	Main	2	-	empty	Add new sample

Showing 1 to 10 of 99 entries

« < 1 2 3 4 5 ... 10 > »

Log Out

Figure 4.5: Screenshot of route /tracker, the sample tracker.

The **Sample Tracker** is the latest addition to AMORE; it consists of a single table containing info about the names and locations of every slot, plus the Standard ID and name of the sample present in it (if any). The table is styled and scripted using **DataTables** which enables searching and sorting on the data shown.

For occupied slots the "Sample ID" field contains the STD-ID of the sample present, which is also an hyperlink to the eLabFTW page of the sample: this way the user can easily access the Resource directly on eLab for more advanced modifications. The "Action" button shows the text «*Move sample*».

For available slots the sample's name and ID are left empty and greyed out, and the "Action" button shows instead the text «*Add new sample*» - since there's no present sample to move elsewhere.

4.3.1 Moving a sample

A sample can be added to an available position (pulled) or moved away from an occupied position (pushed); a sample can be moved even if no position is currently assigned to it, and it can be removed from the laboratory entirely (empty position). The only difference is how the pages for an

available slot and an occupied one are rendered and how they allow the user to perform one of the aforementioned operations (push or pull).

Figure 4.6: (Left) Page of a position currently occupied; (right) page of a position currently available.

If a slot is occupied the only operation permitted is pushing the sample - moving it elsewhere. The page will show a summary of the sample and a hyperlink to «*Open on eLabFTW*» the page of the associated Item. The drop-down menu is rendered in the same way as the "Position" menu in the /create route - only showing the names of the available positions - plus a «** Remove from chamber **» option which will simply set the new position of the sample to a null value. Submitting the form will restore the availability of the position.

If a slot is available the only operation permitted is pulling a sample from elsewhere. The user will be prompted with the numerical univocal ID of the Resource on eLabFTW - NOT the Standard ID; submitting the form will result in the (re)allocation of the sample to the selected position, marking it as occupied.

4.3.2 Export Sample Locator as JSON

Another button - still to be positioned in the main page - will allow the user to download a copy of the Sample Locator Experiment with a timestamp included. The downloaded resource is a JSON object parsed to only contain strictly necessary data, like the names of every slot and the samples they currently hold; a "Date" key contains the date and time in which the processing prior to the download has occurred.

The JSON downloaded can also serve as a backup file since the informations inside of it can be easily reverted to an eLabFTW entity.

4.4 Export data on sample

This section explains a utility which currently doesn't exist, with no preliminary test yet made. The back-end of this feature is extremely easy to program: a GET request will download an object from a certain endpoint, dump it to a new file, compress everything and save it on the user's PC.

In practice the user will have another page on the website (probably /export or /checkout) where they will be allowed to select an Experiment or a Resource - initially by eLabFTW-ID then by other means like Standard ID - and download a compressed folder with JSON files of both the original entry and its related assets.

The JSON files downloaded are meant to be used for backup and for importing data to a NOMAD instance through my colleagues' applications.

Chapter 5

Codebase and folder hierarchy of AMORE

What follows is an in-depth analysis of AMORE's codebase. The root folder of the software contains the files used for setup (`setup.sh`, `dockerfile` and `config.json.example`), the `requirements.txt` file, a copy of the license, the repository's README file and three subfolders: `tests/` contains every script or other files used to test the API capabilities, `docs/` contains the software documentation written in AsciiDoctor - for admins, users and future maintainers - and `amore/` contains the software's modules, init files and assets (templates and style).

Inside the `amore` subfolder there are three modules - `gui`, `api` and `var` - plus the already mentioned `scan_elab.py` script and a `classes.py` file containing the class `Tracker` used to parse and extract data from the Sample Locator (see section 5.4.4).

5.1 The *gui* module

The `gui` folder contains every file used by Flask to generate the web application. The templates are written in the `static/` and `templates/` folders and by definition are immutable; most of the logic behind the page generation is contained in the `app.py` file.

5.1.1 The starting point of the web service: *app.py*

When starting the server, the first file called by Flask is always the `app.py` file - which contains every instruction necessary to initialize the Flask app,

configure upload limits and other parameters, allow the generation and set the timeout of session cookies and most importantly define the available routes.

`app.py` is the only file in the codebase to import the *flask* library for obvious reasons; it also uses *secrets* to generate secure session cookies, *datetime.timedelta* to set the session timeout, *os* to get environmental variables and AMORE modules *client.py*, *utils.py* and *auth.py* (see 5.2 for more details).

Flask functions Due to the complexity of the Flask library, only the following objects are imported and used by AMORE:

- The **Flask** class implements a WSGI application and acts as the central object. From the Flask documentation: «Once it is created it will act as a central registry for the view functions, the URL rules, template configuration and much more»;
- **request** (small-r) is used to call the methods used during a user request and define the behaviour of the server in response;
- **render_template** is the function which renders a web page starting from a given template - identified by name;
- **redirect** creates a redirect response object - in layman's terms it's used to redirect a user visiting a certain route under certain conditions to another route;
- **flash** and **get_flashed_messages** are functions used to handle pop-up messages to alert the user if something goes wrong;
- **session** allows server-side handling of session cookies.

5.1.2 Initial setup of *app.py*

The app is initialized as an object in the Flask class and its attribute *secret_key* is set to a random hexadecimal token regenerated every time the server is restarted. The app's max content length is extended from 16 MB to 100 MB to allow for larger file uploads during sample creation.

Before specifying the routes, an `@app.before_request` instruction is added to enable session permanence and set its lifetime to 10 minutes, otherwise the session would expire every time the browser is closed. After

that a documented *check_session* function is defined with the objective of checking if the current session cookie contains a valid, non-null API key; if that's not the case, the user is redirected to the login page.

Be aware that **this rule is enforced on every defined route**, which means that only the login page is accessible for unauthenticated users as any other route redirects to */login*. The validity of the API key is checked through the auth module's *check_apikey* function.

5.1.3 Routes

Login, logout and index The */login* route behaves differently with methods GET and POST: while in the first case the *login.html* template is directly rendered, in the second case the API key submitted is verified and - if valid - authenticates the user. If the user is already authenticated the */login* route will redirect them to the index.

The */logout* route simply clears the session cookie and redirects to the login page with a success (green) pop-up message; it also checks if the user is authenticated because if the session cookie has already expired for other reasons (e.g. timeout, logout in another tab, etc.) it also returns an error message (see figure 4.2, bottom picture).

The */ (index)* route renders the page seen in figure 4.3, which simply directs the user towards one of AMORE's features.

Create and create_sample The */create* route renders the Sample Creation page (figure 4.4), fetching lists of available slots, batches and proposals through *client.py* functions; the lists are passed to the template and elaborated with Jinja.

When the user fills and submits the Sample Creation form the data is sent to a special route - */create_sample* - which only accepts POST requests. The server takes the information submitted in the form as strings or integers and handles any eventual attachments via a dedicated *utils.py* function, then it patches the Item associated to the substrates batch used for the creation of the sample, reducing the number of available pieces by one; after all of this the client function *create_sample* is called and the user is redirected back to */create*, where one or more pop-up messages are shown (success with STD-ID, low-on-stock warning, out-of-stock warning, error). Attachments stored in temporary files/folders are deleted.

Tracker and single slot routes Similarly to the `/create` route, the `/tracker` route fetches a list of every slot and associated sample from the tracker object, then renders a table as seen in figure 4.5.

By using the cached list of slots (file `amore/var/slots.json`) the app also creates a different subroute of `/tracker` for every single slot present in the list (`/tracker/<slot>`). For every route, the tracker object is analysed to check if that specific route is available and if not which sample it contains; all these informations are then passed to the `slot.html` template and depending on the availability of the slot one of the pages shown in figure 4.6 is rendered.

Move_to_new special route Just like the `/create_sample` route, the `/move_to_new` route only accepts POST requests. Submissions of any operation executed on a position page (see section 4.3.1) redirect to this route regardless of the availability of the slot - therefore without differentiating *push* and *pull* operations. ID, old and new positions of the sample are passed to `client.py` function `move_to_position`, which will patch the Sample Locator entry on eLab updating the target sample's location.

5.1.4 Templates and other assets (HTML, CSS and JS)

Apart from the DataTables contents all HTML, CSS and JavaScript used for this project is stored in the `gui` module subfolders.

- The **templates** folder contains HTML files to generate every page with variable data; HTML files also contain JavaScript used to create and manage pop-up messages.
- The **static** folder contains CSS for styling the pages.

Initially to save time HTML and CSS code has been generated with LLM DeepSeek-R1; eventually as the project grew bigger than a single page the LLM had trouble keeping track of every request I've made, therefore most of the original code has been readapted or straight up remade by me personally. The JavaScript code is all AI-generated - which is evident since pop-up messages which are supposed to vanish automatically after 30 seconds persist indefinitely.

5.2 The *api* module

Originally the **api** folder was meant to only contain functions programmed to interact with eLabFTW's API; this still holds true with the exception of the **utils** submodule whose purpose is providing a series of utilities mostly unrelated to the API like functions for normalization of strings, sanitization of user inputs or attachments handling.

5.2.1 The *auth.py* submodule

The initial idea to implement the login system was creating a file containing every function used to establish and manage the user session. Eventually the only function created in the **auth** submodule is **check_apikey**, which takes in input the API key provided by the user, checks if the key is not null (empty string), then sends a GET request to the eLabFTW `apikeyes` endpoint and:

- If the response has status code of the 5xx class (server errors) the function raises an error message prompting the user to «Try asking the sysadmin» - since a server error is usually not jurisdiction of the user;
- If the response has status code 403 ("Forbidden") or any other code of the 4xx class (client errors) the function raises the error message «Invalid API key»;
- Else the response contains a dictionary of names, hashes, last usage times and permissions of every valid API key associated with the user making the request; the function also calls the last key used (the one submitted by the user, used to make this very request) and checks the value of its `can_write` field:
 - If `can_write` is set to 0 it means the key doesn't have writing permissions (read-only), therefore (by version 0.2.0) the function raises an error message warning the user that their key - while valid - cannot be used on AMORE;
 - If `can_write` is set to 1 the key has writing permissions and will be used by AMORE; another GET request is made to the `users/me` endpoint from which the function returns the string containing the full name of the user.

Every error is shown to the user via pop-up messages. In case of success the full name of the user is printed in every page of the application.

5.2.2 The *client.py* submodule

The **client** submodule is the one which required the most time to work on and is probably the most important. Imported libraries are *os*, *requests*, *json*, *datetime.datetime*; it also imports the AMORE utility *normalize_to_int* (section 5.2.3) and the *Tracker* class from *amore/classes.py* (section 5.4.4).

The first segment of the file declares the variables used frequently by its functions, namely:

- **full_elab_url**: URL of the API root endpoint (base URL of eLabFTW instance followed by "api/v2/", base URL is taken from environmental variable *ELABFTW_BASE_URL*);
- **experiments_url**: URL of the /experiments API endpoint;
- **items_url**: URL of the /items API endpoint;
- **ssl_verification**: boolean which enables or disables HTTPS-only requests;
- **cat**: dictionary with ID's of every Category taken from the *categories.json* cache file (see section 3.3.4).

"Sample Locator / Experiment" section After the first segment the functions are grouped in "sections" divided by long lines of comments written to catch the eye of the viewer. The "Experiment section" contains functions made to work on the /experiments endpoint, like the unused **create_experiment** - made as an exact copy of *create_sample* then edited to handle many more inputs and elaborate them in more complex manners (for instance it takes strings with goals, procedures and results of the experiment and turns them into a single HTML string assigned to the experiment's "body" field).

Function **sample_locator** looks up every Experiment whose name contains the string "Sample Locator" on eLab through a caps-insensitive search query and tries to get the ID of the Experiment whose name matches exactly the string (the official Sample Locator, not to be confused with its "snapshots" which also have a timestamp in their names); if the Experiment is found it uses its ID to send a GET request to the resource-specific endpoint and assigns the JSON obtained to a variable **tracker** (of class *Tracker*) which it then returns. This object is essential in handling the positions of every sample, which is especially evident when

we see how it is called and handled by functions **add_to_position** and **move_to_position**: they both take an API key, a Sample ID and the sample's new position as input, but the latter also takes the sample's old position. What they do is open the *tracker* object, read its metadata through the *tracker.meta* attribute, then change the value of the old position field to *None* (*move_to_position* only) and set the value of the new position field to the ID of the Sample; the new metadata is dumped in a string and added to a *patch* dictionary, which is then attached to a PATCH request and sent to the URL of Sample Locator to update the Experiment's parameter.

"Sample" section The next five functions all handle a part of the process of creation of a new Sample on eLabFTW. **get_new_sample** looks up and returns the eLab Sample Item with the highest value for its "STD-ID" extra field - value that is later passed to AMORE utility *id_generator* to generate the next STD-ID (section 5.2.3). **upload_attachments** uploads any file attached by the user via POST request to the resource-specific endpoint `/items/{id}/uploads`. **batch_pieces_reducer** patches the Substrates Batch chosen by the user during sample creation to reduce its "Available pieces" value by one; while this function doesn't handle directly the warning messages for depleted batches, it returns the number of remaining pieces to *app.py* which then decides if it needs to flash a warning or not (see section 4.2.1).

The most important functions are **create_sample** and **patch_sample**: the latter is encapsulated in the former since the creation of the Sample must always precede its modification. The operations are executed in the following order:

- Every parameter given by the user is taken as input (API key, title, tags, position, batch, etc.) plus the new STD-ID generated by *utils.id_generator*;
- The new sample is created via POST request with title, tags and template; up to eLab version 5.1.15 every other parameter is refused and must be passed with a PATCH request¹;
- With the eLab ID of the new Item it processes a PATCH request to add the additional data - extra fields included;

¹eLabFTW GitHub Issue #5480: "[API Items endpoint] New /items can't be provided with preset "body", "metadata" and "rating" via curl".[3]

- The Sample Locator is patched to place the new sample in the empty slot chosen; any attachment is uploaded to the new sample.

"Data for form building" section The last three functions are needed to build the "Sample Creation" form, as they return lists of available slots, batches and proposals which the user can select to populate the new Sample. **get_available_slots** gets a list of the available slots through the *tracker.getavailable()* method, then return it sorted alphabetically by name. **get_substrate_batches** looks up every Item of the "Substrates Batch" Category and returns a list of those with at least one available piece. **get_proposals** simply looks up and returns every Item of the "Proposal" Category.

5.2.3 The *utils.py* submodule

The **utils** submodule contains mainly utilities to elaborate strings, files and objects. The only function handling an HTTP request is **get_std_id** which scans the Item database for the list of all samples whose titles contain a given location code ("Na", "Sa", "Rm"...) then returns the highest value for a STD-ID - regardless of the sample to which it belongs.

STD-ID generation The highest ID is then passed to **id_generator** which as the name suggests generates a new STD-ID based on location, current year and last ID. The function takes as input the city of the new sample ("Location" field in the Create Sample form) and converts it to a province code using the dictionary stored in *amore/var/locations.py*; the city code is stored as variable but also passed to *get_std_id* to fetch the last Integer ID for that location from eLabFTW. The year of creation of the most recent sample is taken as the result of integer division between the ID and 1000 - which returns the first two digits corresponding to a short year (24, 25...); if the year of the last sample is not the current year - which implies no samples have been created yet during the current year - the unique ID of the new sample is set to 1, otherwise it's set to the last unique ID (remainder of the integer division of the previous Int. ID by 1000) incremented by one. The function then outputs a tuple with both the new Integer ID (current year \times 1000 plus new unique ID) and its equivalent full Standard ID (in format {location}-{%y}-{unique}, e.g. "Na-25-000").

Normalization Function **normalize_to_int** is only used once by the client and attempts to turn any non-integer variable to an integer: if the

variable is already an integer the function outputs the same value without touching it, if it's an empty string or a `NoneType` variable it outputs 0 and if it's any other entity (for instance a string containing a number) it attempts to convert the string to integer - if it fails the output is still 0.

Handling attachments Utility `attachment_handler` takes in input a list of files, loops through every item, checks if the file size is less than 100 MB and if this limit is observed the file is moved to a temporary folder (".uploads") where it's easier for the client to recall it for uploading. The files in the temporary folder are then removed through utility `tmp_remover`.

Miscellaneous Last but not least a "miscellaneous" section is dedicated to smaller utilities like `slots_shortlist`, function that simply opens the file `amore/var/slots.json` and loads its contents to a dictionary, or returns `FileNotFoundError` if the file doesn't exist.

5.3 The *var* module

The `var` folder contains dictionaries used by AMORE to generate routes and Standard ID's, and also to lookup the (eLab) ID's of certain Item Categories by name to avoid hard-coding human incomprehensible numbers.

categories.json The `categories` file contains a single-line object containing names and ID's of each Category on the given eLabFTW instance. Requesting Items of a certain Category from eLab is only possible if the ID of the Category is known, and these ID's are assigned to a Category in such a way that if the Category is deleted and remade for whatever reason the ID also changes, which is especially tedious if AMORE is to be configured to target a fresh install of eLabFTW - where the ID's are probably different. This file exists to avoid hard-coding every ID of every Category in multiple requests throughout the codebase.

slots.json The `slots` file contains a larger dictionary with mostly immutable data about the various sample locations listed in the Sample Locator Experiment (see sections 2.2.2 and 5.4.4); this data is used by `app.py` to generate every `/tracker/<slot>` subroute for pushing or pulling a sample from a certain slot (end of section 5.1.3) without having to request and process data of the Sample Locator on every refresh of the page.

locations.py The **location** submodule contains a dictionary - *prov_code* - containing names and codes of every Italian province; it also contains a single function, *location_to_code* which accepts the name of a province and returns its code if the name corresponds to an item, or "Xx" otherwise. This function has been created early in the development, is extremely inefficient and badly programmed, serves a small part of the sample creation process and it's currently being deprecated since that part of the software has been reworked.

The JSON files (*categories* and *slots*) are generated every time the *scan_elab.py* script is run successfully; the *locations.py* file is hard-coded.

5.4 Other important files

5.4.1 *setup.sh* and the dockerfile

As stated before, to simplify installation and updates AMORE can be installed via Docker. For this purpose a dockerfile has been created; since AMORE doesn't work together with other more complex software no Docker-Compose file is yet available.

The **setup.sh** script can be used as a setup wizard for AMORE on server if the software requirements are met (section 3.3.1). The script opens with a "presentation" section and the declaration of three functions:

- **check_elabftw** looks for an eLabFTW instance in the URL provided by the user in a non-foolproof way: it sends a cURL GET request to the base URL provided - page "/api" which returns code 404 - and looks for the word "eLabFTW" in the header of the response, if the word is not present the check is not passed;
- **normalize_url** takes the same provided URL and makes sure it's properly written by removing eventual pre-existing protocols and trailing slash then adding them back again - so that nothing changes if the URL was already properly written;
- **parse_and_export_json** opens a JSON file (default "*config.json*") and exports all of its keys as environmental variables; it returns error if binary jq is not installed.

The following section of the code checks the script's arguments for valid options, listed in section 3.3.2 and more deeply explained here.

- **--literal:** sets the env. variable *literal_mode* to true, which later instructs the program to skip the URL normalization - doesn't call the function *normalize_url*; the user is warned before being prompted for the URL.
- **--force:** sets the env. variable *force_mode* to true, which later instructs the program to skip the check for a valid eLabFTW at the given address - doesn't call the function *check_elabftw*; the user is warned after the URL is read.
- **--quick:** sets the env. variable *SLEEP* from one to zero, disabling time delays between prompts.
- **--file:** looks for the file *config.json* in the current directory and passes its contents to function *parse_and_export_json*; subsequently, before every prompt the program checks if the variable it's looking for has already been assigned, and if that's the case the section is skipped; if no file is found the program exits with status 1 (error).

After a brief message to notify the user about the license chosen for AMORE (MIT), the program prompts the user for three things: the URL of the eLabFTW instance the user would like to link to AMORE, the option to only allow secure connections (which is preferred but will not work if the eLab instance has a self-signed certificate or none) and a valid API key (read-only or read/write) which will not be stored. The program will recap the parameters given by the user, after which it will check if Docker is installed (command `-v docker`) and running (`systemctl is-active docker`); future plans are to move this check at the beginning since not having Docker properly setup will result in interruption of the program which can be frustrating after having to enter all these informations.

The program then overwrites the *config.json* file with the variables it gets from the user strictly needed to run *scan_elab.py*, then executes `docker build`:

```
docker build \  
  --build-arg URL=${ELABFTW_BASE_URL} \  
  --build-arg VERIFY=${VERIFY_SSL} \  
  -t amore .
```

The dockerfile itself consists of just 15 commands. The base image used is **python:3.12** from DockerHub (line 1).

```
1 FROM python:3.12 # base python image
2 WORKDIR /app
3 COPY . .
4 RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
5 EXPOSE 5000
6 ENV PYTHONPATH="/app"
7 ARG URL
8 ARG VERIFY
9 ENV ELABFTW_BASE_URL=$URL
10 ENV VERIFY_SSL=$VERIFY
11 RUN python3 amore/scan_elab.py
12 RUN rm -f config.json
13 ENV FLASK_APP=amore/gui/app.py
14 ENV FLASK_ENV=production
15 CMD ["flask", "run", "--host=0.0.0.0"]
```

The contents of the folder are copied to the image (3), pip is run to install the dependencies (4), port 5000 is exposed (5). *scan_elab.py* is executed inside the container (11) to download and cache informations on eLab Categories and positions; as seen later (5.4.3) the script gets the environmental variables required from the *config.json* file, which is then removed from both inside (12) and outside the image. With the proper env. variables (6-10, 13-14) the command to execute is **flask run --host=0.0.0.0**.

Finally the following command starts the container:

```
docker run -d -p ${HOST_PORT}:5000 \
    --name amore-container --restart always amore
```

The `-d` option stands for "detach", `-p` ("publish") specifies the port to expose the service through (host port before, container port after), the `--name` option assigns a name to the container and `--restart` declares the policy with which Docker must restart the container - "always" means restart every time docker.service starts, including machine reboots, even if the container has been stopped manually.

5.4.2 Environmental variables in *config.json*

A template file called *config.json.example* is included in AMORE's repository: it contains all four environmental variables used by AMORE to know which eLabFTW session it must interact with, how and as who. The variables are:

- **ELABFTW_BASE_URL**: base URL of eLab instance, must always contain the protocol prefix, the port number if different from 80 (HTTP) or 443 (HTTPS) and the trailing slash (e.g. "https://myelab.mysite.net:42069/" or "https://mysite.net/elabftw/");
- **API_KEY**: temporary API key of any user to download and cache data from eLab through *scan_elab.py*; it can be read-only since no writing operations are done during setup;
- **VERIFY_SSL** (string): set to "True" or "False" depending on whether the eLab instance has a CA SSL certificate;
- **HOST_PORT**: number of the port the installer wants to expose AMORE through - note that declaring this variable in the config file is the only way to select a port different than default (5000).

5.4.3 Scanning eLabFTW with *amore/scan_elab.py*

The script **scan_elab.py** is mostly detached from the rest of the software, in the way no other file uses it on runtime; it can only be run directly since no instruction is executed if `__name__` is not equal to `__main__`. The script imports *requests*, *os*, *json*, *datetime.datetime* and client function *sample_locator*.

The contents of *config.json* are decoded to a Python object and assigned to global variable *config*; variables *ELABFTW_BASE_URL*, *API_KEY* and *VERIFY_SSL* are called from *config*, and if they are not found the script will attempt to call them from the environment: if *ELABFTW_BASE_URL* is not found in *config* nor as environment variable the program quits with error, but if no *VERIFY_SSL* is found the script will set True as its default value instead.

The API key is different since if no *API_KEY* value is found in *config* nor as environmental variable the script will ask the user for input, and a total of three attempts are granted before the script quits. *scan_elab* will verify the validity of the API key with its own version of the *auth.check_apikey* function; the "read-only" error is handled in a way which allows read-only keys to be used nonetheless. If the key is valid the program:

- Calls a function **scan_for_categories** to get the categories from the *items_types* API endpoint, then parses the result and saves it to *categories.json*;

- Calls the client module's **sample_locator** to get the "shortlist" of all the positions in the laboratory, then saves it to *slots.json*.

5.4.4 *classes.py* – The *Tracker* class

Although it's called **classes** the file only contains a single class named **Tracker**. Due to the complexity of the Sample Locator as a JSON object, in order to correctly manage the data the most efficient solution was deemed to create a class with a pre-defined logic and its own methods, then assign everything AMORE downloads from the Experiment to an object of this class.

To create a *tracker* object the class needs a dictionary as input (`json.load(...)`). The init method allows attributes *title* and *id* which are not really useful, plus:

- **self.links**: list of linked Items, which should match with the list of every sample located in an instrument;
- **self.meta**: value of the key "metadata", serialized as Python object;
- **self.groups**: object with names and ID's of every extra field group - which corresponds to the list of all the instruments (section 2.2.2);
- **self.positions**: object with names and associated samples' ID's of every extra field - which means every slot.

getsamples This method returns a list of selected data about samples present in any instrument, regardless of their positions. Every item in the list is a dictionary with ID, Standard ID and proper name of the sample.

getslots This method returns a list of objects containing relevant data about every single slot of every single instrument in the laboratory, including its current availability. First it takes every item in *self.positions*, associates it to the name of its instrument using "`item.get("group_id") == group.get("id")`" as join condition - where *group* is an item of *self.groups* - then splits the name of the slot into *instrument*, *sector* and *slot* codes, checks the presence of an Item ID to assign a value to boolean variable *available* and finally gets name, ID and STD-ID of the sample stored inside the slot - if any.

This method returns a list of dictionaries containing values for the following keys:

- **name:** name of the position in *INST-Sec-Slot* format (standard nomenclature described in section 2.1.2);
- **shortname:** same as *name* but in compact format - i.e. without spaces;
- **slot:** code of the slot ("*Heater*", "*Fork*", "*1*", "*2*" etc.);
- **sector:** code of the sector ("*Main*", "*LOST*", "*Tip*" etc.);
- **inst_name:** full name of the instrument - taken from *extra_fields_groups* ("*PLD-MODA*", "*Organics Chamber*" etc.);
- **inst_code:** short code of the instrument ("*PLD1*", "*ORG*" etc.);
- **sample_id:** ID of the Sample Item associated to the slot on eLabFTW - null if the slot is empty;
- **sample_stdid:** STD-ID of the sample stored in the slot - null if the slot is empty;
- **sample_name:** given name of the sample stored in the slot - null if the slot is empty;
- **available:** boolean set to `True` if no sample is stored in the slot (availability condition) and `False` if a sample occupies the slot.

shortlist This method returns a list of "trimmed" objects similar to those included in *self.getslots* but containing only **immutable** keys and values. Immutable properties are those strictly related to the slots, that is their names, their instruments and their sectors - which do not change over time; on the other hand *mutable* properties are those which change constantly, that is availability and data on the sample stored. In short, the last four keys listed in the *getslots* paragraph are filtered out. This method is used to create the cache file *slots.json* (see section 5.3 on the *var* module).

getavailable The *getavailable* method filters only available slots from the *self.getslots* list, making it perfect for rendering the drop-down menu in the sample creator page.

isthisloss This method returns a sublist of *getslots* which only includes positions in *LOST* sectors. While not yet used actively by AMORE it could be useful to quickly remove unrecoverable samples away from the original position. Its name is also a reference to the popular internet meme².

²["Is This Loss?" | Know Your Meme](#)[8]

```
.
|-- amore
|   |-- api
|   |   |-- auth.py
|   |   |-- client.py
|   |   |-- __init__.py
|   |   |-- utils.py
|   |-- classes.py
|   |-- gui
|   |   |-- app.py
|   |   |-- static
|   |   |   |-- flash.css
|   |   |   |-- styles.css
|   |   |   |-- tracker.css
|   |   |-- templates
|   |   |   |-- create_sample.html
|   |   |   |-- index.html
|   |   |   |-- login.html
|   |   |   |-- slot.html
|   |   |   |-- test.html
|   |   |   |-- tracker.html
|   |-- __init__.py
|   |-- scan_elab.py
|   |-- var
|   |   |-- categories.json
|   |   |-- __init__.py
|   |   |-- locations.py
|   |   |-- slots.json
|-- config.json
|-- config.json.example
|-- dockerfile
|-- docs
|-- LICENSE
|-- README.md
|-- requirements.txt
|-- setup.sh
|-- tests
```

Directory tree of AMORE; folder names are coloured in teal.

Chapter 6

Changes in the infrastructure and conclusion

The work presented in this thesis was the response to the necessity of migrating the process of data collection in our labs from the old, unreliable and obsolescent physical notebook to a more trustworthy digital infrastructure. In the process some degrees of freedom are taken from the single scientist to minimise errors during creation or modification of resources on the eLN, although they will still be able to freely modify the data submitted via AMORE directly from eLabFTW's interface which will of course remain available with a public IP address, making it reachable from inside and outside the faculty.

At present time due to the constant overlapping of my professional duties and my academic pursuits many things have been left unfinished. Other than that the original pipeline has been heavily shrunk down leaving out additional assets like NetBox or snipeit which not only could have been important in the management of the laboratories' infrastructures but they also could have posed a satisfying challenge with a certain academic value, both in their setup on server and in their compilation. One last regret is not having cooperated more with my colleagues in Naples and all over Italy during the past months, as my personal project slowly drifted away from their pipelines.

6.1 Deploy of eLabFTW and AMORE

eLabFTW and AMORE are to be tested through the month of May, during the preparations of the new NFFA-DI lab. If everything goes smoothly

they will be officially adopted by next summer before the inauguration of the aforementioned faculty, and paper notebooks will be removed completely from MODA.

In the meantime AMORE is to be tested and patched against external attacks and exploits; during this time it will be exposed locally (which means it will only be accessible from within the Physics Department through a local IP or a FQDN¹ to be assigned) so that scientist can beta-test and get accustomed to the software while small improvements are pushed on a daily basis to accommodate any needs of the researchers. Since AMORE will probably run on the same VM as eLabFTW - which has a public address and can be reached from outside the department - firewall rules must be put up on university's firewall to deny any connection from outside over the port exposing AMORE. When the software is deemed secure enough and if the authentication method can be improved to include some sort of MFA then AMORE too might be exposed over the internet, but considering the risk related to unauthorized accesses it cannot be taken too lightly.

6.1.1 Backup policies

AMORE does not store permanent data. The only data stored by the software are cache files, which can be easily rebuilt on occurrence. The original code will stay on GitHub and many of my personal devices at least until next year, and a copy of the codebase will be stored on the server and in the backups of the VM.

At a later time the backup policy might be reworked to make use of eLabFTW's **BorgBackup** integration: this is a powerful command-line tool used to generate, schedule and manage backups with deduplication (removal of duplicate data), lossless compression and encryption of the archives. Backups of just the eLabFTW's database make it easier to recover specific data (e.g. on a certain experiment that has been deleted permanently) since the elements present in the archives are human-readable JSON objects and not VM images.

¹Fully Qualified Domain Name. E.g. amore.fisica.unina.it.

6.2 Future improvements to AMORE

Other than the data export/checkout feature described in section 4.4 and the security improvements planned before and during deploy, a to-do list of changes, tests and implementations needed can be found in the GitHub repo's README file. The most important planned modifications can be divided in four categories.

- **Data validation.** The user will always find a way to screw up something, which is why the input they provide has to be validated - for instance to check if the user provides a valid ID while moving a sample to a position - and sanitized - which means it must be tested against benign and malign code injections from the user; this can usually be achieved by simply not allowing certain special characters (like slashes or curly brackets). AMORE in particular should be safe from template injection since all the variables handled by the template engine are taken from lists and objects downloaded from eLabFTW, which might still pose some risk if an eLab entry is poisoned with malicious code.
- **Error handling.** Currently AMORE flashes pop-up messages to the user with confirmations if the operation is successful, errors if something goes wrong and warnings for various other reasons; these pop-ups already print custom messages that explain exactly what went wrong (for instance if the API key provided is read-only). A needed improvement is further enhancing the level of detail of error messages by assigning a code to every message - correspondent to a full explanation of the issue on the user manual - or alternatively by adding "Read more" hyperlinks in the messages to send the user to an online help page.
- **Code documentation.** AsciiDoctor documents are to be compiled with detailed instructions on how to maintain, install and utilize the software; the documents - which will be probably put online on the same website as AMORE as either HTML pages or PDF files - should be comprehensive, extending beyond this thesis' explanations and the inline comments I've provided to include three dedicated manuals: one for end users, one for sysadmins covering network and setup configurations and one for the maintainer which will update the software after my contract is due - detailing the codebase structure, dependencies, and development practices.

- **Cooperation with my colleagues' applications.** The software developed by my colleagues take as input data downloaded directly from eLabFTW by the user, which is what the export feature is needed for, and uploads it on a NOMAD instance in NeXus-compliant format; another idea would be to automate the periodic (or controlled) download and parsing of data from eLab to push it automatically to NOMAD taking the responsibility of doing it manually from the researcher's hands.

6.3 Parallel work as system administrator

During the previous 10 months - since July 2024 - I've also been working full time as system administrator for CNR-SPIN, which as explained before is the first reason I haven't been able to achieve what I originally desired to. The most crucial parts of my job in Naples are all related to the **migration from the old LAN** to the new infrastructure; although these tasks have been for the most part external to this Master's course they do not stray too far away from the objectives of NFFA-DI since without a functioning network there is no digital infrastructure.

The **migration itself** has taken up most of my time. Previously the entire department's network was managed by the INFN - which was also in charge of handling the traffic and manually assigning the IP addresses. The new network has two VLAN's (*Virtual Local Area Network*) dedicated to CNR-SPIN, one for public IP addresses - which are to be assigned manually - and one for private addresses only - in DHCP²; every machine in our labs and offices - computers, printers, servers, instruments, the punch clock etc. - has been reconfigured to automatic IP assignment, its printer drivers and other network-related utilities have been reinstalled, its cables have been replaced and the Ethernet ports to which it's plugged have been reconfigured to our internal VLAN. In all of this I was also available for technical support as the only on-site CNR-SPIN sysadmin.

Before and during the migration the old deteriorated network infrastructure has begun to break, with faulty ports left hanging from the wall and worn out UPS units leaving the floor racks without power.

²*Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol*, network management protocol used for automatically assigning IP addresses and other communication parameters to devices requesting a connection to the network.

A problem with **eduroam** has occurred and still occurs to date with the wireless controller installed in the new WLAN which doesn't allow connections specifically for users in the *cnr.it* (and subdomains) realm, meaning that at least since the beginning of the year users with *spin.cnr.it* and *cnr.it* credentials have not been able to connect to eduroam from the Physics Department alone. I will not go into details about this issue - which for its extravagance and complexity would require another thesis.

I've also recovered an old dismissed server from the INFN to add a third node to our Proxmox cluster to use for a remote access service (like RustDesk) and a new NextCloud instance for SPIN Naples.

You can see how without wireless connections and with downtimes caused either by the migration or by accidents like [the fire of Fuorigrotta](#) of last December and its consequent blackout, or even by faults in the old infrastructure before the migration, many employees have often found themselves without internet access, requiring me to find makeshift solutions to put administrative employees and researchers back online - solutions which took more time to plan than to implement.

Planned improvements on the infrastructure behind our laboratories

Two planned improvements on the infrastructure are the setup of a **RustDesk** server for remote access to lab and office PC's and the purchase of a new high-performance server. The RustDesk will replace the TeamViewer used in MODA - with explicit permission of the software company - and will allow remote technical assistance for the users in Monte S. Angelo.

6.4 Conclusion

While AMORE is developed according to the supervisor's requirements and is perfectly functional on theory, no tests have been made yet and many improvements are still to be pushed to production. Laboratory inventory, backup policies and our own remote desktop service are next in line, where the former in particular will be standardized and implemented when our eLabFTW is cleared of every test entry and ready for production.

AMORE will be kept updated with new modifications based on user feedback, and will be adapted as necessary when eLabFTW version 5.2.0 is officially released.

Appendix A

Glossary

Some of the definitions found in this glossary have been taken from Wikipedia and rephrased into layman's terms for a wider audience to understand.

A.1 General terms and expressions

- **Accessibility:** «*Once the user finds the required data, they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.*»¹
- **AMORE:** Acronym of "*Autonomous Management of Outputs for Research Efficiency*", name of the software developed for this thesis' project.
- **Back-end:** The part of the software which works out of the user's sight, for instance the server which runs the code and manages the database.
- **bcrypt:** the algorithm eLab uses to encrypt passwords and API keys; while most people consider it deprecated ever since a serious vulnerability has been found back in 2014, more recent versions of bcrypt still hold strong.
- **BYOK:** Acronym of "*Bring Your Own Key*", it refers to a system in which the user must store its own access key in a secure way; in our case the key is a string of random hexadecimal digits too long to be

¹As stated on the GO FAIR Foundation's [official website](#)[9].

memorized which requires the use of a secure password manager like KeePassXC.

- **CLI:** "*Command Line Interface*", an interface which allows users to interact with a piece of software through typed commands or plain text navigation, and is therefore harder to navigate and more suited for advanced users.
- **DMP:** Acronym of "*Data Management Plan*", a structured document that outlines how research data will be managed throughout the life-cycle of a project and after its completion; in our case, it contains guidelines on who's responsible for our instruments, who's the data curator, what outputs are produced by our instruments (formats, throughput), what are our storage and publication policies regarding collected data, under which license will it be published, etc.
- **Docker:** A set of platform as a service software which use OS-level virtualization to deliver software in packages called *containers*. Docker can be used to minimize two types of problems: dependency hell - where a single software drags a huge amount of dependencies during installation and might not work if even one of those is deprecated or a different version is installed - and "It works on my machine" - which is self-explanatory.
- **eLabFTW:** Free and open source "secure by design" eLN developed to easily keep track of experiments and resources; it can be self-hosted by a research institute (server installation via Docker) and can be used for collaboration even in large teams. Link to the GitHub repository.
- **ELN/eLN:** Acronym of "*electronic Laboratory Notebook*", which is a digital system for replacing the traditional paper laboratory notebook, improving accessibility and findability of the data harvested in it. Among the most relevant in the context of NFFA-DI we have Jupyter, NOMAD and of course eLabFTW.
- **EOL:** Acronym of "*End-of-Life*", which refers to software that is no longer supported and updated - which is almost always synonym of "insecure".
- **FAIR data:** Data which meets the FAIR principles of *Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability*.

- **Findability:** «*The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.*» ¹
- **Framework:** A software structure providing pre-written code which can be easily adapted to simplify the creation of different software by for instance reducing repeating tasks or reinforcing best practices - serving as a base for multiple, very different projects.
- **Front-end:** The part of the software that users interact with directly, for instance the web pages they visualize on their browsers.
- **Git:** Versioning software widely used by developers to keep track of modifications on their codes and restore old versions if something stops working. A Git folder containing all the metadata to keep track of the code modifications is called a *repository* (or *repo*), and every "snapshot" or "version" made during development is called *commit*.
- **GitHub:** Website owned by Microsoft which serves as a public hub to create, store, publish and share Git repositories.
- **GUI:** "*Graphical User Interface*", an interface which allows users to interact with a piece of software through graphical elements - rather than through typed commands or plain text navigation (see *CLI*'s).
- **HDD:** Acronym of "*Hard Disk Drive*", what is commonly called hard disk.
- **HTTP:** Acronym of "*Hypertext Transfer Protocol*", an application layer protocol and the foundation for data communication for the World Wide Web; web servers usually expose port 80 or 8080 for accepting HTTP requests.
- **HTTPS:** HTTP Secure, an application layer protocol which encrypts the informations exchanged between client and server, providing protection towards man-in-the-middle attacks, eavesdropping and tampering; web servers usually expose port 443 for accepting HTTPS requests.
- **Hyphen-minus:** Unicode character with code U+002D, present in most keyboards as the only minus sign/dash. Very similar to hyphen

(U+2010), non-breaking hyphen (U+2011), minus sign (U+2212), en dash (U+2013) and em dash (U+2014).

- **IDE:** Acronym of "*Integrated Drive Electronics*" and also called *PATA* is a standard interface for storage devices superseded by SATA.
- **Init system:** The first process to be executed by the OS during startup.
- **Interoperability:** «*The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.*» ¹
- **jq:** lightweight command-line JSON processor.
- **Linux:** Largely used kernel for operating systems; the term is also used to refer to OS' based on this kernel, although the proper term would be *Linux distributions* or *distros*.
- **MFA:** Acronym of "*Multi-Factor Authentication*", method of authentication which only allows access to a service after a user's identity is proved by two (or more) pieces of evidence (factors); if only two factors are required the expression "*Two-Factor Authentication*" (**2FA**) can be used instead.
- **NFFA-DI:** Acronym of "*Nano Foundries and Fine Analysis - Digital Infrastructure*"; it's a national proposal for upgrading the pre-existent European NFFA infrastructure with the objective of raising the quality, reproducibility and overall competitiveness of Italian research in nanoscience. More at nffa-di.it.
- **OFED:** Acronym of "*Overarching FAIR Ecosystem for Data*", the digital ecosystem built within NFFA-DI meant to collect, archive, visualize, share and analyse NFFA-DI Data.
- **OS:** Acronym of "*Operating System*", system software that manages computer hardware and software resources.
- **PCI:** Acronym of "*Peripheral Component Interconnect*", computer bus for special peripherals like dedicated graphics cards, Ethernet/Wi-Fi modules or acquisition cards; superseded by PCI Express.
- **PLD:** Acronym of "*Pulsed Laser Deposition*", deposition technique where a high-power pulsed laser beam is focused inside a vacuum chamber to strike a target of the material that is to be deposited.

- **Reusability:** «*The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.* » ¹
- **SMART:** In the context of mass storage it's the acronym of "*Self-Monitoring, Analysis, and Reporting Technology*", monitoring system included in hard drives and solid state drives which analyses the status of the device and stores important data regarding its health.
- **smartctl:** Binary used to access SMART data of a device, requires root permissions.
- **Systemd:** The most popular init system on Linux-based OS'.
- **Template engine:** Software designed to populate templates with data to generate multiple documents or programs with the same base model, HTML, style and more, but showing (or handling) different data; sometimes used as a synonym for *template language*, the language with whom the templates are written.
- **VM:** Acronym of "*Virtual Machine*", a software which emulates a physical machine with its own architecture, OS, etc. A software made to handle multiple VM's on the same server is called a *hypervisor*.
- **Web app:** Short for *web application*, an application whose front-end is a web interface accessed via browser.
- **Web framework:** A framework designed specifically to support the development of web applications.
- **Web server:** A software (and the underlying hardware) used to expose a website to the network, capable of accepting and replying to HTTP or HTTPS requests; examples of popular web server software are Apache HTTP Server and nginx.
- **Windows:** The most popular desktop operating system. Somehow.
- **XPS:** *X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy*, photoemission spectroscopy technique consisting in analysis of electron population spectra obtained by irradiating a surface with X-rays.

A.2 Python3 glossary

- **Class:** A blueprint for creating objects in Python, defining attributes (data) and methods (functions) that the objects will have.
- **CRUD:** Acronym of "*Create, Read, Update, Delete*", representing the four basic operations in persistent storage - in our case eLab's API.
- **datetime:** A module in Python's standard library for manipulating dates, times, and time intervals.
- **Dictionary:** A mutable, unordered collection of key-value pairs, where keys must be unique and hashable; easily convertible from and to JSON.
- **dotenv:** A Python library that reads key-value pairs from a `.env` file and loads them as environment variables.
- **Flask:** A lightweight web framework for Python used to build web applications and APIs.
- **Framework:** A pre-built structure (like Flask) which provides tools and libraries to streamline application development.
- **Jinja:** A templating engine for Python used by Flask which dynamically generates HTML.
- **JSON:** Acronym of "*JavaScript Object Notation*", a lightweight data interchange format that Python can parse (`json.loads()`) and serialize (`json.dumps()`).
- **List:** A mutable, ordered sequence of elements that can be of mixed types.
- **Module:** A Python file containing reusable code (functions, classes, or variables) that can be imported.
- **OODB:** Acronym for "*Object-Oriented DataBase*", a database management system in which the data is contained in objects used in object-oriented programming, rather than tables like in relational databases.
- **os:** A standard library module for interacting with the operating system (most notably file operations, environment variables).

- **requests:** A popular HTTP library for making web requests (GET, POST, etc.) to API's or web servers.
 - **DELETE method:** An HTTP request method used to delete a specified resource.
 - **GET method:** An HTTP request method used to retrieve a specified resource.
 - **PATCH method:** An HTTP request method used to update a specified resource - even partially.
 - **POST method:** An HTTP request method used to send data to a specified resource.
- **REST API:** Acronym of "*Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface*", an architectural style for designing web services that use standard HTTP methods.
- **secrets:** A standard library module for generating cryptographically secure random numbers and tokens.
- **venv:** Python's built-in tool for creating isolated virtual environments to manage dependencies of a project; extremely useful for quick tests if the user doesn't want to install all the required packages on root level.

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